

Deep water

CR1002 — a promising rice cultivar for rainfed waterlogged conditions

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CR1002 is a new rice strain derived from a cross of CR70 and Pankaj, made at the Central Rice Research Institute, Cuttack. It was included in a yield trial of 20 long-growth-duration rices in West Bengal under rainfed, ill-drained conditions in 1978 kharif. An unprecedented flood submerged all entries.

The experiment was in randomized

Yield and performance of the different strains exposed to severe flooding, West Bengal, India, 1978.

Designation	Growth duration (days)	yield (t/ha)
CR1002	154	3.5
IET5656	160	1.8
CO38	156	1.5
IR34	158	1.3
Pankaj (control)	166	1.3
IR4219-35-3-3	173	1.3
IET3257	160	1.0
CR1009	172	1.0
CR1006	184	0.5
CR1011	173	0.4
IET5633	173	0.0

block design with four replications. Fertilizer was applied at 80-40-40 kg NPK/ha. At 46 days after transplanting the experimental plot was completely submerged for 4 days. The water remained at a depth of 75 to 55 cm for 10 more days. CR1002 had 10% dead tillers and IR4219-35-3-3, 66%. Other entries had from 75 to 98% dead tillers.

The severe flood stunted the plants and delayed their maturity (see table). CR1002 yielded highest — 3.5 t/ha — followed by IET5656.

Such flash floods are common in kharif in low-lying areas in West Bengal and other parts of India. ■

Pest management and control DISEASES

Seed transmission of *Rhynchosporium oryzae*

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The survival of *Rhynchosporium oryzae*, the causal agent of leaf scald disease of rice, was studied in the laboratory using the standard agar plating and blotter methods of detection. Seeds of the susceptible breeding line IR1487-372-1-1 were collected from a naturally infested field, stored at four temperatures (20, 25, 30, and 35°C), and examined periodically for the presence of the pathogen.

The presence of *R. oryzae* on seeds was detected through seed plating on potato-dextrose-agar medium (PDA), and the blotter test. The blotter test detected higher infestation than the plating method did after 14 weeks of seed storage. The highest recorded rate of infested seeds was 90% for the blotter test and 47.5% for plating (see table).

The pathogen survived as long as

Percentages of seeds infested with *Rhynchosporium oryzae* at storage temperatures of 20, 25, 30, and 35°C, as determined by the blotter and plating methods.

Weeks in storage	Seed infestation ^a (%) at								
	20°C		25°C		30°C		35°C		
	AD	SD	AD	SD	AD	SD	AD	SD	
<i>Blotter method</i>									
2	0	0	0	0	0	0	30.0	0	
6	20.0	40.0	20.0	40.0	20.0	20.0	50.0	10.0	
8	20.0	0	10.0	10.0	60.0	80.0	10.0	10.0	
10	10.0	10.0	10.0	0	40.0	50.0	60.0	50.0	
12	10.0	40.0	10.0	10.0	30.0	70.0	80.0	40.0	
14	40.0	50.0	30.0	0	70.0	30.0	40.0	30.0	
16	70.0	80.0	30.0	40.0	60.0	70.0	60.0	70.0	
20	20.0	40.0	50.0	40.0	70.0	50.0	50.0	50.0	
24	70.0	50.0	40.0	10.0	70.0	60.0	40.0	80.0	
28	30.0	90.0	40.0	60.0	70.0	90.0	60.0	60.0	
<i>Plating method</i>									
2	2.5	47.5	22.5	17.5	32.5	27.5	32.5	30.0	
6	15.0	35.0	17.0	15.0	30.0	22.5	30.0	30.0	
8	27.5	30.0	25.0	40.0	30.0	40.0	27.5	42.5	
10	32.5	25.0	22.5	27.5	20.0	27.5	22.5	20.0	
14	15.0	17.5	10.0	10.0	17.5	32.5	30.0	30.0	
16	15.0	20.0	17.5	22.5	10.0	30.0	25.0	2.5	
20	35.0	27.5	30.0	15.0	35.0	27.5	32.5	30.0	
24	21.5	42.5	25.0	30.0	12.5	15.0	20.0	21.5	
28	35.0	27.5	30.0	20.0	22.5	25.0	22.5	37.5	

^aAD = air-dried, SD = sun-dried.

7 months at all of the storage temperatures in both air- and sun-dried

samples. The high percentage of transmissibility and the length of survival